

Mega Satellite Communication Networks Harnessing Machine Learning for Next-Gen Design and Operation.

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Take away

We need to connect !

2019, close to 87 per cent of individuals in developed countries used the Internet, compared with **only 19** per cent in the least developed countries [1]

B. Al Homssi, A. Al-Hourani, K. Wang, P. Conder, S. Kandeepan, J. Choi, B. Allen, B. Moores “Next Generation Mega Satellite Networks for Access Equality: Opportunities, Challenges, and Performance”, IEEE Communications Magazine, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.001.2100802>

[1] United Nations, Report of the Secretary-General Roadmap for Digital Cooperation June 2020

[2] Measuring digital development Facts and Figures 2021 International Telecommunication Union Development Sector

Satellite service classes

Fixed satellite services (FSS)

- Traditional **bent-pipe**
- Majority of current FSS market

High-throughput satellites (HTS)

- Applies multi-beam
- Typically in GEO orbits

Traditional land mobile satellite (LMS)

- Typically for handheld small terminals
- Voice services
- Low bandwidth data

IoT-over-Satellite

- Narrowband
- High delay (for delay tolerant applications)

Mega / Dense Massive satellite constellations

- Towards integrated satellite / terrestrial networks
- Potentially one network for all applications
- **Direct-to-device or Direct-to-cell**

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Mega Satellite Networks

- High density of satellites (also the term “**Massive**”)
- **Global coverage** (or near-global)
- Shorter distance -> lower **latency**
- Multi-spot coverage (Similar to HTS)
- **Intersatellite link** opportunity -> reduce infrastructure requirements
- IoT-over-Satellite can still be supported

Dynamic Network Topology

- Potentially **lower delays** than terrestrial optical networks
- Network is highly **dynamic**
- Offers high redundancy
 - Satellite-to-Satellite
 - Satellite-to-ground

K Dakic, C. C. Chan, B. Al Homssi, S. Kandeepan, A. Al-Hourani, "On Delay Performance in Mega Satellite Networks with Inter-Satellite Links", EEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), 2023

Examples (Dense Constellations)

Example: OneWeb 636 satellites (29/06/2023)

Example: StarLink (Space-X) 4275 satellites (29/06/2023)
TLE from <https://www.celestrak.com/>

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Technical Challenges

Radio channel uncertainty in the Q/V bands

Spectrum availability and **Interference**

Integration with terrestrial networks

Performance **modelling** (Hybrid networks / Large constellations / dynamic traffic)

Constellation design and optimization – Topology optimisation

Intersatellite network (ISL) – Optical, THz

Network and Physical layer **security**

AI in Satellite Radio Channel

Case 1: Channel modelling for Q/V bands

- C band is totally congested, Ka/Ku will approach capacity soon.
- Q/V bands are a “**gold mine**” of spectrum.
- However, both the **severity and variability** of fading is much higher in Q/V is much higher
- The need for **time-domain channel prediction** -> proactively inform MAC layer to take the needed action

Satellite access in LEO Mega constellations

- Satellites are in a **continuous relative motions**
- **Multiple** satellites could be used to connect to the ground terminal
- Which one to use depends on the **forecasted fading**

Real time
prediction
of Q/V
channel

- Allow operators to build higher data rate modem -> faster internet

Q/V
Modelling
and
simulation

- Allow operators to model and simulate accurate scenarios -> better performance on the long run

Results

B. A. Homssi, *et al.*, "Deep Learning Forecasting and Statistical Modeling for Q/V-Band LEO Satellite Channels," in *IEEE Transactions on Machine Learning in Communications and Networking*, vol. 1, pp. 78-89, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TMLCN.2023.3286793.

AI for Satellite Radio Spectrum

Interference is quite different from space !

- **Shared** spectrum: very large interference from terrestrial services / other constellations
- **Dedicated** spectrum: interference from ground terminals / other satellites

A. Al-Hourani, "Interference Modeling in Low-Altitude Unmanned Aerial Vehicles," in IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, vol. 9, no. 11, pp. 1952-1955, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2020.3009302.

Machine Learning for Spectrum

- Detecting transmission **opportunities** (time / space / frequency)
- Machine learning can significantly improve the **accuracy** of detection

B. A. Homssi, A. Al-Hourani, Z. Krusevac and W. S. T. Rowe, "Machine Learning Framework for Sensing and Modeling Interference in IoT Frequency Bands," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 4461-4471, 15 March 2021, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2020.3026819.

Cognitive Satellite Radios (CogSat) Project

- Develop advanced **cognitive** and **AI radio techniques** for adaptive satellite communications
- Improve the spectral efficiency
- Mitigate interference in satellite communications

More on the project:

<https://smartsatcrc.com/research-programs/cognitive-satellite-radios/>

AI for Satellite Communication

Classical / AI Hybrid approach

- AI is not always the go-to solution. There are **well-structured problems** that are known to have optimal (non-AI) solutions
- E.g. Receiving of communication signal under thermal (Gaussian) noise
- To the contrary, AI is shown to be more robust for demodulating communication signal under **interference**
- The use of a **hybrid** architecture to switch between classical receiver and AI-based receiver

K. Dakic, B. Al Homssi, M. Lech and A. Al-Hourani, "HybNet: A Hybrid Deep Learning-Matched Filter Approach for IoT Signal Detection," in *IEEE Transactions on Machine Learning in Communications and Networking*, vol. 1, pp. 18-30, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TMLCN.2023.3270131.

Spiking Neural Networks

- Satellite are **power and energy limited**
- **Onboard AI processing** typically requires large amount of power
- **Spiking neural networks (SNNs)** is new promising class based on analog neuromorphic hardware
- The use of SNN **to detect communication signals** in the presence of uplink interference.

K. Dakic, B. Al Homssi, and A. Al-Hourani, "Spiking-UNet: Spiking Neural Networks for Spectrum Occupancy Monitoring", IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC) 2024 conference, WCNC 2023

K. Dakic, B. Al Homssi, S. Walia and A. Al-Hourani, "Spiking Neural Networks for Detecting Satellite Internet-of-Things Signals," in IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems, doi: 10.1109/TAES.2023.3334216.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/TAES.2023.3334216>

Performance modelling

Modelled Constellation Types

Performance analysis (the **Random Model**)

- Analytic modelling allows a rapid **calculation** of the expected **performance bound**
- Capturing **inter-satellite interference**

B. A. Homssi and A. Al-Hourani, "Modeling Uplink Coverage Performance in Hybrid Satellite-Terrestrial Networks," in IEEE Communications Letters, vol. 25, no. 10, pp. 3239-3243, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/LCOMM.2021.3103942.

A. Al-Hourani, "An Analytic Approach for Modeling the Coverage Performance of Dense Satellite Networks," in IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 897-901, April 2021, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2021.3049179.

Constellation optimization (**Altitude**)

- Constellation altitude impacts
 - **Pathloss**
 - Satellites **availability**
 - Coverage **footprint**
 - **Interference** levels
- Satellite altitudes can be optimized for achieving desirable performance metrics

A. Al-Hourani, "Optimal Satellite Constellation Altitude for Maximal Coverage," in IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 1444-1448, July 2021, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2021.3069751.

The impact of increasing the is more prominent on optimal altitude than the number of satellites in the constellation as indicated in Fig. 3. This figure is using $N = 200$ satellites.

Constellation optimization (Altitude)

A. Al-Hourani, "Optimal Satellite Constellation Altitude for Maximal Coverage", IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, 2020.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/LWC.2021.3069751>

Simulation time = 0.0 min
Constellation size= 196 Satellites
Altitude = 1000 km

Simulation time = 0.0 min
Constellation size= 196 Satellites
Altitude = 400 km

Beamwidth optimization

B. Al Homssi and A. Al-Hourani, "Optimal Beamwidth and Altitude for Maximal Uplink Coverage in Satellite Networks," in IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 771-775, April 2022, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2022.3143498.

Satellite pass-duration modelling

Random model

Walker delta constellation

Satellite pass-duration modelling

- What long does the satellite dwells (by average) ?
- The pass-duration is impacted by
 - Altitude
 - Beamwidth
 - Constellation configuration

$$\bar{T}_p \approx T_o (-a \tan^2 \varphi_{\max} + b \tan \varphi_{\max} + c)$$

- Simple formula can capture the geometric availability (i.e. isotropic antenna beam)

$$\bar{T}_p [\text{min}] \approx 9.31 \times 10^{-3} h [\text{km}] + 4.68$$

A. Al-Hourani, "A Tractable Approach for Predicting Pass Duration in Dense Satellite Networks," in IEEE Communications Letters, doi: 10.1109/LCOMM.2021.3077557.

A. Al-Hourani, "Session Duration between Handovers in Dense LEO Satellite Networks", IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LWC.2021.3118214>

AI For Satellite Network Security

AI for physical layer security

- **Identifying** wireless devices based on their hardware imperfections
- Ability to detect **hardware** identity based on the physical layer only.
- Ability to detect relay attacks
- Mitigate **spoofing** attacks

D. Huang, A. Al-Hourani, W. S. T Rowe, S. Kandeepan, "Deep Learning Methods for Device Identification Using Symbols Trace Plot", IEEE Transactions on Machine Learning in Communications and Networking, 2023, (Under review).

D. Huang, A. Al-Hourani, S. Kandeepan, W. S. T. Rowe, L. Bulot, and A. Thompson, "Deep Learning Methods for Device Authentication Using RF Fingerprinting", IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication Systems, ICSPCS, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSPCS53099.2021.9660226>

Onboard AI processing

Neuromorphic hardware

- To overcome the current energy-expensive Si-based digital processors new circuit architecture and **materials**.
- Novel materials** (including metal oxides) shows useful decay characteristics suitable for SNN
- Such materials are potential for performing both (optical) **sensing** and **processing**

Aung, T., et. al., S. (2023), Adaptive Convolutional Neural Networks for Enhanced Memory Retention and Restoration in Optoelectronic Vision Devices. Adv. Intell. Syst. 2300069. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aisy.202300069>

Mazumder, A., et. al (2023), Long Duration Persistent Photocurrent in 3 nm Thin Doped Indium Oxide for Integrated Light Sensing and In-Sensor Neuromorphic Computation. Adv. Funct. Mater. 2303641. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202303641>

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Challenges

- **Interference**
- **Integration** with terrestrial networks
- Space debris
- Link **performance** (Q/V band, optical, THz)
- **Onboard** processing (power/energy limitations)
- Network **security**
- **Dynamic** network
- Network modelling:

Opportunities

- New AI-enabled **waveforms** and detection methods
- Radio channel **forecasting**
- Spectrum **sensing** and **classification**
- Traffic forecasting and topology optimization
- **Spoof detection** and physical layer security

“Towards Space Edge Computing and Onboard AI for Real-Time Teleoperations”: <https://ai.jpl.nasa.gov/public/documents/papers/ieee-leo-sats-report.pdf>

Challenges and opportunities

“Artificial Intelligence Techniques for Next-Generation Massive Satellite Networks”
[10.1109/MCOM.004.2300277](https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.004.2300277)